

INFINITE ARTISTIC SPIRITUAL VALUE

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In the history of Turkmen literature, Magtymguly created a unique national way of seeing and feeling the world, man, and expressing his problems artistically in opening the way to the soul of humanity, creating a river of emotions from the artistic word. The development of patriotism, heroism, bravery, high morals, philanthropy in Dana Magtymguly's creations to the level of fine word art went down in history as a national artistic revival of Turkmen literature. According to this fact, Wise Magtymguly's poetic world, which is rooted in the history, today and tomorrow, spiritual development of the people is complex and has a thousand colors.

The literary treasure of the great master of words, his way of view point of the world is wide, original, at the same time delicate and elegant, fresh and beautiful. The poet's poetic identity is also the same: his era, time scale is unlimited, and his field of action is wide. As far as human imagination and dreams can reach, the thinking of the poet reaches there and reveals to us its mysterious artistic reality. There, he forms his complex thought and moral world, driven to deep wisdom. In Magtymguly's creativity, the field of such formation includes the events of the throne, the throne, the earth, the events of fantasy (mythical), legend, fairy tales, and philosophies about them. This kind of literary breadth, the elegance of the art of words, various behaviors, artistic means, traditions, meaning, which are used to admonish the people, morals, actions, wisdom form the artistic and spiritual world of Magtymguly. In order to create such a world, the poet focuses on the unified meaning of each work, the unified thought that it promotes. As a result, its depth, breadth and depth are revealed in the aforementioned artistic field. It is impossible to limit that area, to control it, to bring it to a policy of its own accord. Accordingly, Magtymguly's multi-colored imagination, poetic world, in most cases, depends not only on his personal life, but also on his artistic spiritual world. The poetic personality in Magtymguly's works was also formed in such a context, his poetic thought and appeal often appeared in the artistic and spiritual world of the master of words.

The Turkmen people paid special attention to the individuals who completed the advantageous jobs in the country and created delightful stories about them. Folktales have been passed down from language to language and have become an indelible asset in the history of folklore and literature. As our father Magtymguly said: "If a sign from person is left in the world, his name will be immortalized, and that is the foundation". The poet recited these lines with care. A great symbol of his pride remained, an indelible name remained.

Folk works about Magtymguly are artistic products of views of the great son of the Turkmen people, it is a set of complete works of art, perfected on the basis of a harmonious combination of historicity and artistry, nationalism and commonality, moral philosophy and life conflict. The root of its perfection rested on the forces that made the development of life, public morals, science, culture and speech art of the Turkmen people. The persistence of that power, the deep establishment of a new direction in the history of the people and the world of artistic society is directly connected with the name of Magtymguly and the service of his graduates. Accordingly, we call the character of Magtymguly artistic people's a hero who has

changed from simplicity to a complex character. The public interest also demanded it. The way people understood Magtymguly, if they heard his heart sounds, the people also understood their eldest son in the same way: they looked at him as a pure example of humanity, humanity, morals and conscience. Over the years, this attitude has grown, settled in hearts, and turned into holiness. This led to the creation of an artistic character that grew out of public interest over time. The stories of Magtymguly's life, works, and period of his life have enriched the people to the point where the name of the city has become famous.

The depiction of Magtymguly is a hero, whose artistic image in stories has unique characters and characteristics in Turkmen folklore and fiction. Its place in poetry and narrative, its characteristics and generalities are as follows.

The character of Magtymguly's artistic depiction traces its origin from certainty, the reality of life. Art, imagination, and generality based on metaphors are based on concreteness and draw from the wellspring of concreteness and truth. The artistic character of the poet's depiction also moves in concrete or real life events. In his character, actions, moral and life views, noble qualities characteristic of Magtymguly: patriotism, bravery, humanitarianism, whose values are artistically reflected.

The people created vivid artistic characters of the great poet Magtymguly Pyragy and his well-intentioned comrades of that time. Magtymguly's artistic character in the stories fully meets the rules of creating an artistic character of folk art. Accordingly, all the signs, including the artistic image, were reflected in the event of a specific character.

Magtymguly, like a sentimental poetic hero in the stories, is adorned with good ideas and attitudes, a hero who is able to distinguish between kindness and cruelty, wisdom and ignorance, and similar contradictions and stand on the side of good things.

The poetic personality of the great master of words that befriends and fraternizes the people, the artistic image of the people in the stories is an inflexible artistic spiritual value that cleans, enriches and educates the spiritual world of the people during the Revival of the new age of stable state.